

P4DMA: Unlocking High-Performance RDMA Traffic Generation on Programmable Switches

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Abstract—Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA) is a key technology in modern data centers, enabling low-latency and high-throughput communication. However, evaluating RDMA performance and validating network designs often requires costly hardware setups or simulation tools with limited performance and realism. In this work, we present P4DMA, a system that leverages programmable switch ASICs to generate realistic high-performance RDMA traffic. By implementing RDMA traffic patterns using the P4 language, P4DMA enables researchers and practitioners to generate RDMA workloads at line rate, without relying on traditional RDMA NICs (RNICs). With Tofino’s traffic generation capacity of up to Tbps, P4DMA offers a novel approach to stress and evaluate RDMA-capable infrastructures, and accelerate the prototyping of new RDMA-based applications.

Index Terms—RDMA, P4, Traffic Generation, Network Testing

I. INTRODUCTION

Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA) has evolved from its original application in high-performance computing (HPC) to a widely adopted mechanism in modern cloud data centers [1], [2]. RDMA enables the network interface card (NIC) to transfer data directly between the network and application memory, bypassing the CPU. This architecture reduces latency, increases throughput, and minimizes CPU overhead [3]. These characteristics make RDMA particularly effective for latency-sensitive and bandwidth-intensive workloads, such as the training of large language models. Consequently, RDMA—especially RDMA over Converged Ethernet version2 (RoCEv2)—is increasingly being integrated into data center networks to meet rising performance demands.

Despite its efficiency, RDMA poses significant challenges to the network infrastructure. One major issue stems from the use of Priority-based Flow Control (PFC), which can lead to problems such as congestion spreading, head-of-line blocking, occasional deadlocks, and PFC storms in large-scale deployments [4]. Another critical limitation concerns connection scalability: as the number of active connections (aka Queue Pairs (QPs)) surpasses a certain threshold, RDMA performance reduces sharply due to cache misses caused by frequent context switching across connections. To address these challenges, recent efforts have proposed mitigation

Fig. 1. P4 Direct Memory Access (P4DMA) Overview.

strategies, including enhancements in RoCEv2 NIC (RNIC) implementations [5] and switch-assisted mechanisms [6].

However, testing RDMA-based solutions introduces additional challenges. These solutions must achieve line-rate performance—typically 100Gbps or higher—while also handling the stateful nature of the RoCEv2 protocol. Software-based tools are constrained by the number of available CPU cores, a limitation that becomes more pronounced when generating traffic for stateful connection protocols. Tools such as TRex¹ and Scapy² include packet builders capable of reproducing RoCEv2 packets with Base Transport Header (BTH) and RDMA Extended Transport Header (RETH). However, they do not support the handshake mechanisms required to establish and manage stateful RDMA connections. In contrast, hardware-based tools—such as Tofino switch-based platforms, Norma [7], PIPO-TG [8], P4R [9], and Hypertester [10]—also have limitations. These tools either do not support RDMA traffic generation or provide only partial functionality. Additional solutions, including FPGA-based RoCEv2 implementations [5] and Direct Telemetry Access (DTA) [6], can generate RDMA packets but are not designed for general-purpose network testing. These approaches are purpose-specific, do not support all RDMA operations, and lack scalability for high-throughput traffic generation.

Existing methods offer partial support; however, a dedicated traffic generation tool remains necessary to reproduce RDMA operations and ensure effective testing of RDMA-based solutions and environments. To address this gap, we propose P4 Direct Memory Access (P4DMA), a system that leverages the programmability and performance capabilities

¹<https://trex-tgn.cisco.com/>

²<https://scapy.net/>

Fig. 2. P4DMA Architecture Overview.

of the Tofino switch³ to generate and emulate RDMA traffic. Figure 1 illustrates the architecture used for implementing and evaluating the proposed traffic generator. In this setup, the user connects to the Tofino switch and specifies the desired traffic configurations. The P4 switch then initiates the RDMA handshake with the RNIC through its built-in traffic generation module. After the handshake is completed, RDMA operations are issued from the switch to the RNIC, which replies accordingly. Throughout this process, the user receives real-time feedback on the traffic transmitted to the RNIC, enabling continuous monitoring and evaluation.

II. ARCHITECTURE & IMPLEMENTATION

In this section, we provide a high-level overview of the components and their interconnections within the architecture. Furthermore, we present the implementation, detailing the strategies used to develop the available features.

A. Architecture

RNIC. First, the RNIC must be configured to receive network traffic by creating Scalable Functions (SFs) and attaching them to a physical port of the SmartNIC BlueField-2 via the E-Switch. The SF interfaces are then connected to the RDMA application running on the ARM Subsystem, as presented in Fig. 2. This setup enables packet flow between physical interfaces, SFs, and the application. Finally, the RDMA application is launched in listening mode.

Control Plane. In the control plane (as illustrated in Figure 2), the network traffic settings are defined, including the specification of traffic patterns, the pipeline generation port, port bandwidth, and the designated switch port for packet forwarding. After these configurations are established, the execution module takes responsibility for compiling the P4 programs, initializing the P4 switch, configuring the ports, installing the table entries, and starting traffic generation in accordance with the specified settings.

P4 Switch. Within the P4 switch, traffic configuration parameters—such as generation port, output port, and throughput—are specified through table entries. The ingress parser is responsible for extracting RDMA headers and applying match-action rules accordingly. Control tables then define the

Fig. 3. P4DMA Workflow.

appropriate forwarding behaviors, including packet field modification, congestion control mechanisms such as Priority Flow Control (PFC), and selection of the egress port. In the egress pipeline, RDMA packets are assigned to egress queues based on their priority level and traffic class, aiming to optimize both latency and throughput. The packet forwarding logic ensures that RDMA traffic reaches its intended destination.

User Station. The execution of P4DMA begins and ends at the user station. It starts with the user providing configuration inputs, continues with real-time traffic monitoring during runtime, and concludes with the collection of results and logs corresponding to the executed RDMA operations.

B. Workflow

In the workflow of P4DMA (illustrated in Figure 3), the user is responsible for configuring the environment, which includes compiling and executing P4DMA on the Tofino switch and running the RDMA application on the RNIC. The user also provides the necessary input to initiate the execution of P4DMA. The handshake phase, managed by the control plane, defines the procedures for establishing and maintaining RDMA connections. Once the connections are in place, RDMA operations are executed in the data plane to perform the actual data transfers.

³<https://github.com/barefootnetworks/Open-Tofino>

C. Implementation

RDMA Headers in P4. In RDMA over Converged Ethernet (RoCE), multiple headers are employed to ensure correct packet transmission. RoCEv1 operates directly over Ethernet using EtherType 0x8915, whereas RoCEv2 encapsulates RDMA packets in UDP over IP, enabling routing across IP subnets. A fundamental component of the RDMA protocol stack is the Base Transport Header (BTH), which includes fields such as the Opcode – used to specify RDMA operations like Read, Write, and Send – the Partition Key (P_Key), and the Packet Sequence Number (PSN), which supports reliable data transmission. In P4, these headers are extracted during the parsing stage, enabling the programmable switch to inspect and manipulate RDMA packets as needed.

RDMA Handshake. As shown in Figure 3, the Connection Manager (CM) is responsible for handling the handshake process and establishing RDMA connections between endpoints. The procedure consists of three main steps. First, the initiator (i.e., the P4 switch) sends a CM Request containing the Queue Pair (QP) number and Packet Sequence Number (PSN) to initiate the connection. In response, the RNIC returns a CM Reply, which includes its QP number, PSN, Remote Key (R_Key), and Remote Virtual Address (RVA), thereby enabling the initiator to access the registered memory region. Finally, the initiator sends a CM Ready-to-Use message, indicating that the connection setup is complete and the QP is prepared to perform RDMA operations.

Congestion Control in P4. We implemented Priority Flow Control (PFC) for congestion management by monitoring the switch’s internal buffers. When buffer occupancy exceeds a predefined threshold, the switch generates a PFC Pause Frame to signal upstream devices to reduce transmission for a specific PCP priority. This mechanism relies on monitoring tables that track buffer usage. Upon detecting congestion, the switch injects a PFC Frame into the network, pausing only high-priority flows. Once congestion is alleviated, a PFC Unpause Frame is issued, allowing traffic to resume without packet loss.

III. SETUP & DEMONSTRATION

Setup. Our experimental setup (see Fig. 4) comprises a Tofino Wedge100BF-32X switch running SDE version 9.9, connected via a 100G QSFP28 DAC to a NVIDIA BlueField-2 SmartNIC. The Tofino switch executes the P4DMA P4 program, which is responsible for high-performance transmission of RDMA operation packets, as well as the implementation of related functionalities. A Python-based controller initiates the RDMA connection through a handshake and populates the P4DMA tables with the necessary request information. On the BlueField, a simple DOCA-based RDMA application runs on the ARM subsystem, listening for and processing incoming connections and operations. Both the switch and the SmartNIC report performance metrics to the P4DMA monitoring server.

IV. FINAL REMARKS

In this work, we introduced P4DMA, a novel traffic generator that enables realistic RDMA traffic generation directly in

Fig. 4. Demonstration Setup.

the data plane using programmable switches. By leveraging the capabilities of Intel Tofino and the P4 language, P4DMA emulates RDMA-like behavior at line rate, eliminating the need for traditional RNICs. This approach offers a practical and cost-effective solution for testing, validating, and benchmarking RDMA-based systems. P4DMA opens new opportunities for advancing research in RDMA technologies, in-network computing, and data center architectures. For future work, we plan to expand P4DMA’s support for a broader set of RDMA operations and explore its integration with larger-scale testbeds and heterogeneous infrastructures. Additionally, incorporating adaptive traffic patterns and more complex workload profiles will further enhance its applicability to real-world scenarios.

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